

Electrochemically Induced Michael Addition Reaction: An Overview

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Abstract

Due to its high potential for the formation of carbon-carbon bonds, Michael addition reaction is one of the closest reactions to the heart of synthetic organic chemists. Electrochemistry presents a very stimulating and divergent resource for selective oxidation and reduction in organic chemistry, generating activated species, for example radical anions or radical cations. In this review, we try to underscore usefulness of electrogenerated Michael addition reaction with the hope of encouraging synthetic organic chemists to contemplate it, as an efficient and green strategy when it is required in their designed multi-step reaction pathways.

Keyword: carbon-carbon bonds, electrosynthesis, Michael addition reaction, Multicomponent reaction